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Research Article

Structural characteristics of the control region of the *Beaufortia kweichowensis* mitochondrial genome

Abstract

In present study, we identified the structural characteristics of the *Beaufortia kweichowensis* mtDNA control region using the next-generation sequencing method. Result showed that the control region could be further divided into three parts, including the extended termination associated sequence domain (ETAS), the central conserved domains (CSB-F, CSB-E, CSB-D) and the conserved sequence block domains (CSB-1, CSB-2, CSB-3), and their conserved sequences were identified. Additionally, we found the ETAS domain could be folded and form a 25 bp loop, which are usually considered to play an important role in mtDNA transcript termination. Finally, we reconstructed the phylogenetic relationship among the family of Balitoridae based on the nucleotide sequence of the control region, result showed that the Balitoridae can be divided into two clades, one clade is Gastromyzoninae and the other is Homalopterinae, and the *B. kweichowensis* was grouped into clade Gastromyzoninae and shared a close relationship with *B. zechuanensis*.

Introduction

Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) is a circular double-strand DNA with a 15–20 kb length in animals, and it usually encodes 37 genes, including 13 protein-coding genes (PCGs), 22 transport RNA (tRNA), and 2 ribosomal RNAs (rRNAs) [1,2]. To date, mtDNA has been widely used for genetic research, taxon classification, phylogenetic evolution research and population studies attribute to its fast variation, maternal inheritance, rapid evolution and lack of recombination [3,4]. Recent years, the mitochondrial genome database growth rapidly following the fast development of high throughput sequencing technology [5], which might provide more chance for scientists to solve the biological mystery in the future.

The control region, also called displacement-loop region (D-loop), is a DNA fragment with fastest evolution rate in mtDNA because it composes of the single strand nucleotide [6]. It can be divided into three domains, including the extended termination associated sequence domain (ETAS), the central conserved domains (CSB-F, CSB-E, CSB-D) and the conserved sequence block domains (CSB-1, CSB-2, CSB-3) [7,8], and it also has been extensively used for phylogenetic analyses and populational genetics researches [9,10].

Fish is one of the most amount groups in vertebrate, and now more than 30000 species has been discovered [11]. Thus far, more than 200 fish genome and 1000 fish mitochondrial

genome has been sequenced and deposited into NCBI database, and these data are available for all researchers, thus then some important scientific issue such as the evolutionary relationship of fish has been well investigated [12,13], which also will be helpful for species classification and phylogenetic analyses in these groups.

B. kweichowensis (Fang) is an endemic fish of the upper reaches of the Beipan River of China, belonging to the family of Balitoridae (Cypriniformes), has not yet been well studied about its phylogenetic evolutionary status [2]. In present study, the structure of control region of *B. kweichowensis* mtDNA was investigated, and the conserved sequences also was identified. Subsequently, the phylogenetic tree of the family Balitoridae was reconstructed based on the sequence information of mtDNA control region, which could be helpful to establish the evolutionary status of this species.

Material and Methods

Sample collection and DNA isolation

One adult *B. kweichowensis* used in this study were obtained from Conservation and Utilization of Fishes resources in the Upper Reaches of the Yangtze River Key Laboratory of Sichuan Province, Neijiang Normal University. A 20–30 mg fin clip was collected and preserved in 95% ethanol at 4 °C. Total genomic DNA was extracted with a Tissue DNA Kit (OMEGA E.Z.N.A.) following the manufacturer's protocol.

Conclusion

The control region of *B. kweichowensis* could be divided in two three domains, and their conserved sequence were identified. Furthermore, a 25 bp long loop domain was found in the ETAS. Finally, the phylogenetic relationship of the family Balitoridae was analyzed, result highly supported the *B. kweichowensis* belongs to the subfamily Gastromyzoninae.

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